

Synthesis of Chalkones from 2-Hydroxy-4-*n*-Butoxyacetophenone

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VARIOUS workers¹ have prepared the chalkones by condensation of resacetophenone and its mono- and dimethyl ethers with aldehydes. It was thought interesting to study the effect of butylation of one of the hydroxy groups on the synthesis of chalkones.

The bromination of chalkones was studied by various workers^{2,3}. They observed that bromination of chalkones gave α - β dibromo derivatives³ but in the case of dihydroxy compounds, it was observed that the nucleus containing hydroxy groups was more reactive than the double bond in the molecule and bromine enters in the nucleus of hydroxy ketones^{2,3}.

In the present communication, resacetophenone 4-*n*-butylether has been condensed in presence of alkali with benzaldehyde; 4-methoxybenzaldehyde^{3,4} methylenedioxybenzaldehyde; 3,4 dimethoxybenzaldehyde

and 4-chlorobenzaldehyde giving the corresponding chalkones. It was observed that presence of *n*-butoxy group in 4-position does not inhibit the formation of chalkones.

Bromination of these chalkones was studied using bromine in chloroform when α : β dibromochalkones were obtained. It was observed that bromine does not enter in the nucleus of hydroxy ketone due to the presence of 4-*n*-butoxy group. The reactivity of the dibromides was examined with potassium iodide in acetone when the original chalkones were regenerated. Hence it was proved that addition of bromine to chalkone took place at double bond.

Experimental

2'-Hydroxy-4'-n-Butoxychalkones: 2-Hydroxy-4-*n*-butoxyacetophenone⁴ (0.01 mol) and the aldehyde (0.011 mol) were dissolved in ethanol (50 ml). Potassium hydroxide solution (40%, 40 ml) was added to above solution with shaking. The mixture was left for 24 hr. at room temperature (25°-30°). On dilution with ice-water and acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) a yellow solid separated. It was crystallised from acetic acid. It gave characteristic orange colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. It gave an orange colour with ethanolic alkali and brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. The chalkones are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—2'-HYDROXY-4'-*n*-BUTOXYCHALKONES

No.	Substituent	Crystal appearance	M.P. °C	Formula	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1	Nil	Yellow needles	84	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₈	76.91	77.02	6.60	6.75
2	4-Methoxy	Yellow needles	126	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	73.48	73.62	6.64	6.75
3	3,4-Methylenedioxy	Yellow needles	147	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅	70.73	70.58	5.76	5.88
4	3,4-Dimethoxy	Yellow needles	110	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₅	70.63	70.79	6.83	6.74
5	3-Methoxy-4-ethoxy	Yellow needles	116	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₅	71.52	71.36	6.90	7.03
6	4-Chloro	Yellow needles	106	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₈ Cl	8.10 ^a	8.17 ^a		

a=It is Cl-analysis

TABLE 2—BENZOYL DERIVATIVE OF CHALKONES

No.	Substituent	Crystal appearance	M.P. °C	Formula	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1	Nil	Yellow wooly needles	86	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₄	77.91	78.00	5.92	6.00
2	4-Methoxy	Yellow needles	103	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ O ₅	77.45	75.34	5.90	6.04
3	3,4-Methylenedioxy	Yellow wooly needles	96	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₆	72.81	72.97	5.29	5.40
4	3,4-Dimethoxy	Pale yellow needles	121	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₆	72.88	73.03	6.15	6.09
5	3-Methoxy-4-ethoxy	Pale brown prisms	122	C ₂₉ H ₃₀ O ₆	73.28	73.41	6.43	6.33
6	4-Chloro	Yellow wooly needles	96	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ O ₄ Cl	10.65 ^a	10.74 ^a		

a=It is Cl-analysis

TABLE 3—2'-HYDROXY-4'-*y*-BUTOXY- α - β -DIBROMOCHALKONES

No.	Substituent	Crystal appearance	M.P. °C	Formula	% Bromine	
					Found	Calc.
1	Nil	Yellow needles	87	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₈ Br ₂	34.92	35.09
2	4-Methoxy	Yellow needles	123	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄ Br ₂	32.81	32.93
3	3,4-Methylenedioxy	Yellow wooly needles	138	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅ Br ₂	31.91	32.00
4	3,4-Dimethoxy	Yellow needles	134	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₅ Br ₂	30.93	31.01
5	3-Methoxy-4-ethoxy	Yellow shining needles	144	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₅ Br ₂	30.31	30.18
6	4-Chloro	Yellow needles	132	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₈ ClBr ₂	39.97 ^b	39.86 ^b

b=It is total halogen

Benzoyl derivative of chalkone ; The benzoyl derivative of chalkone was prepared by heating a mixture of chalkone, benzoyl chloride and few drops of pyridine on water bath for five hours. The compounds are listed in Table 2.

2'-Hydroxy-4'-n-Butoxychalkone- α - β -Dibromide : 2'-Hydroxy-4'-n-butoxychalkone (0.5 g) in chloroform (25 ml) was treated with bromine in chloroform (0.4 ml ; 50%). The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature (25-30°C). Chloroform was removed and the residue was washed with sodium thiosulphate solution (5%) and crystallised from light petroleum ether. The compounds are listed in Table III.

Debromination of α - β Dibromochalkone : A mixture of the above dibromide (0.2 g) and potassium iodide (0.2 g) in dry acetone (25 ml) was refluxed on waterbath at 53°-70° for 2-3 hr. The solid separated after removal of acetone and pouring the contents in water was washed with sodium thiosulphate solution (5%) and crystallised from ethanol. The product was identified as the original chalkone by direct comparison.

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References

1. A. G. PARKIN and J. HUMMEL., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1459
W. H. PARKIN, R. ROBINSON and M. R. TURNER., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1109
A. GÖSCHKE and J. TIMBER., *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3502 ; 1912, 45, 186, Alfred Russel., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 218.
I. Z. SAIYAD, D. R. NADKARNI and T. S. WHEELER., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1737.
D. R. NADKARNI and T.S. WHEELER., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1320.
2. H. P. VANDEWALLA and G. V. JADHAV., *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 28, 125.
3. V. G. KULKARNI and G. V. JADHAV., *J. Univ. Bomb.*, 1954, 35, 17.
4. J. F. EJKAMAHN, F. BERGEMA and I. T. HENARD, *Chemisches Zentralblatt*, 1905, 1. 815.

Synthesis and Antiinflammatory Activity of some 6-[2-Amino-(and substituted amino)-4-thiazolyl] benzothiazoles.

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IN an earlier paper¹, we described the synthesis and antiinflammatory properties of a series of 2-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl) benzothiazoles. These compounds were relatively non-toxic and exhibited significant antiinflammatory activity which in some cases approached that of phenylbutazone. In this communication

we report the synthesis of a series of 6-[2-amino-(or substituted amino)-4-thiazolyl] benzothiazoles (I) with a view to testing their antiinflammatory activity.

R=H, CH₃, CF₃ or C₆H₅
R'=H or Aryl

2-Methyl-6-benzothiazolyl methyl ketone (II) was prepared from *p*-aminoacetophenone which was thiocyanated and then converted to 4-amino-3-mercaptoacetophenone³. The latter was condensed with acetic anhydride in acetic acid to get the ketone (II). Bromination of the ketone (II) in acetic acid (yield 39%)² was improved by carrying out the reaction in chloroform (yield 59%). 6-Benzothiazolyl bromomethyl ketone and its 2-phenyl and 2-trifluoromethyl analogues were prepared according to the method of Burger and Sawhney⁴. Treatment of these bromomethyl ketones with the appropriate thioureas gave the corresponding compounds in the series I^{1,4}.

Preliminary pharmacological screening of some of the selected compounds in the series has been shown that the compounds possess a good level of antiinflammatory activity, though in general they are less active than 2-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl)-benzothiazoles. The highest activity was observed in compound I, R=R'=H, which showed the inhibition of 45% as compared to 53% shown by phenylbutazone in carageenin rat foot edema test⁵ at a dose level of 100 mg/kg.

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